

Transamination Reactions Between Hexamethyl Disilazane and Some Hydrazines

Suraj Prakash Narula and Amrik Singh Dua

When equimolar quantities of hexamethyldisilazane and 1,2 dimethyl or diethyl hydrazines were allowed to react in the presence of catalytic amount of hydrazine hydrochloride in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen, alkylamines produced in the reactions were trapped in melting acetone bath and estimated by titration against standard HCl. N-Methyl N'-trimethylsilyl hydrazines¹ was obtained by fractional distillation (b.p. 96°). (Found, C, 40.3, H, 11.5, N, 23.8 and Si, 24.0%. C₄H₁₄N₂Si requires C, 40.7, H, 11.8, N, 23.7 and Si, 23.7%; yield 35%). Similarly N-ethyl N'-trimethylsilyl hydrazine (b.p. 112°) was obtained. (Found, C, 45.2, H, 11.8, N, 20.7, and Si, 21.5%. C₅H₁₈N₂Si requires, C, 45.4, H, 12.1, N, 21.2 and Si, 21.2%; yield 30%).

Phenyl hydrazine² and 1,1-dialkyl hydrazines³ are known to react with hexamethyldisilazane in the presence of ammonium salts when corresponding trimethylsilyl hydrazines are obtained. However, in this reaction the yields of the products are poor. Literature also reveals that in transamination reactions involving Si-N compounds where less volatile amines are produced, the yield of the silylated product is decreased.⁴

Fessenden and Crowe² have briefly mentioned the isolation of bis (trimethylsilyl) hydrazine by a similar reaction with anhydrous hydrazine in a low yield. This reaction was reinvestigated with a view to isolate pure 1,1-bis-(trimethyl silyl) hydrazine according to the equation

The yields of the products were improved to 55%. But bis-(trimethylsilyl) hydrazine so obtained was again a mixture of its two possible isomers in almost equal proportions as evidenced by G.L.C., infra-red and N.M.R. studies⁵. The two isomers were separated by preparative G.L.C. and subjected to mass spectral analysis. Both 1,1 and 1,2-isomers show molecular ion peaks ($m/e = 176$). The highest mass peak, however, is observed at $m/e = 73$ (i.e., Me₃ Si⁺). The other peaks at m/e 146 and 131 may be accounted for by the loss

1. F. Hofler and U. Wannagat, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1966, **97**, 1598.
2. R. Fessenden and D. F. Crowe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 4638.
3. Z. I. Sergeeva and C. L. Hsieh, *Zhur. Obsch. Khim.*, 1962, **32**, 1987.
4. K. A. Andrianov, G. A. Kurakov, L. M. Khananashvili and T. A. Lomonosova, *Zhur. Obsch. Khim.*, 1963, **33**, 1294.
5. U. Wannagat, F. Hofler and H. Burger, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1965, **96**, 2038.

of CH_3 and NH and two CH_3 and NH fragments from the parent molecule respectively. In the case of 1,2-bis-(trimethylsilyl) hydrazine, the presence of mass peaks at m/e 58 and 43 may be accounted for Me_2Si^+ and the MeSi^+ respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Infra-red and N.M.R. spectra were taken on P.E. 337 with sodium chloride optics and P.E. model R-10 operating at 60 mc/s using benzene external standard respectively. Mass spectra were recorded on AEI-MS 9 while G.L.C. was done on P.E. 452 having $2\text{ m} \times 4\text{ mm}$ column containing silicone oil (40%) on celite operated at 125° . Different fractions were trapped in carbondioxide acetone bath.

Thanks are due to Professor R. N. Haszeldine, FRS, Department of Chemistry, U.M.I.S.T., Manchester, England, for facilities where the latter part of this work was done.

Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh-14.

Received April 13, 1970